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PERCEPTIONS OF CULTURAL EROSION: THE ROLE OF THE GENERATION GAP IN PASHTUN SOCIETY

Aziz Ul Hakim

Ibrahim

Umar Daraz

Mohammad Hussain*

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Perceptions of Cultural Erosion: The Role of the Generation Gap in Pashtun Society

Aziz Ul Hakim

Lecturer, Department of Sociology, University of Malakand, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Ibrahim

Chairman, Department of Sociology, University of Malakand, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Umar Daraz

Assistant Professor, Department of Sociology, University of Malakand, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Mohammad Hussain*

Lecturer, Department of Sociology, University of Malakand, District Dir Lower, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Corresponding Author Email: mohammadhussain.soc@uom.edu.pk

Abstract

This paper discusses how the generation gap has influenced cultural change within the Pashtun culture. The research design was the positivistic approach based on a quantitative research design to investigate the generation gap in the Pashtun society. Proportional random sample was used to get data on 200 male respondents aged 50 years and above in three districts of Malakand Division, which were Lower Dir (n=60), Upper Dir (n=65), and Swat (n=75). The primary data collection tool was a set of interview questions and the answers were broken down using simple frequencies and percentage to determine patterns and trends in the perception of the change in culture and perceptions of intergenerational differences. Empirical and sociological data reveal that old-generations view

the rapid social changes, promoted by modernization, education, urbanization, and exposure to international media, as a threat to the foundational Pashtun values including Nang (honor), *Badal* (justice/revenge), *Melmastia* (hospitality), *Nanawatai* (asylum), respect to el. On the contrary, young Pashtun, who are under the influence of contemporary education, technology and other cultural practices in the world, are progressively adopting individualistic values and behaviors that do not conform to the traditional norms. This deviation comes out through less intergenerational communication, changing professional desires, a change in gender roles, and selective observance of Pashtunwali. The paper emphasizes that the generation gap is more than a mere clash between the two age groups; it is an evolving negotiation of cultures where the old standards are parallel with the new social ways of doing things. Results illustrate the importance

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of interventions that support modernization and cultural sustainability to reduce the amount of intergenerational conflict and maintain social unity within Pashtun communities.

Keywords: Generation gap, Pashtun society, cultural transformation, Pashtunwali, modernization, intergenerational communication

Introduction

The difference between the values, behavior, expectations and communication between the younger and the older cohorts is called generation gap. It has been a normal sociocultural phenomenon that has been studied in most societies and emerges as a result of high modernization rate, development of technology and change of behaviors in the society. The concept of generation gap in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Pakistan has been a more significant area of sociological research. According to researchers, this disjuncture occurs at the stage of education development, urbanization, the onset of digital media, the transformation of gender roles, and the current tribal and communal traditions (F. Ali et al., 2025; Hakim et al., 2025a). Well-developed family ties, patriarchy and adherence to traditional patterns of behaviour such as Pashtunwali are the socio-cultural organization of the province, which provides a unique environment in which the effects of the generation gap may be determined and addressed (Bangash & Habib, 2022; Khan, 2022). Empirical research in KP and nearby Pashtun districts has recently revealed that generation gap is indeed not merely an abstract concept or theory but actually a fact of life and has repercussions in the routine day to day lives of families (Daraz, Ibrahim, et al., 2024). Studies concluded that this gap operates through different mechanisms, including technology, education, migration, changing labour opportunities, etc., which continually reshapes the identity of the youth and parent-child relationships (Daraz, Ali, et al., 2025; Daraz, Ibrahim, et al., 2024; Hakim et al., 2025b). On the one hand, there are district-level and province-specific studies, e.g., the studies in Buner and the previous Khyber District, which reveals a great extent of variations between the attitude of children and parents towards education, gender roles, and media usage (Daraz, Bojnec, et al., 2024; Daraz, Hussain, et al., 2024; Hakim et al., 2024). These studies often record the indications of the generation gap to be poor communication, difference on leisure and dressing, and difference on marriage (which is an evident indication of the generation gap) (Niazi et al., 2021; Wahab et al., 2022). The same experiences are differently understood by the parents and the youth. The young ones will tend to view it as an indication of freedom, aspiration or even choice, whereas the older generation will tend to see it as disrespect

or even erosion (Regan, 2024; Wahba, 2022). In particular, social media has been one of the primary causes of intergenerational distance. It introduces new culture, style and political ideas that are prone to conflict with the conventional values. The researchers allege that the KP process of youth culture digitalization has aggravated the speed of exposure to the global lifestyles, the value difference of which has increased because of the lack of communication between the generations (S. Ali et al., 2025; Ilyas et al., 2023). The other critical problem, which has led to the generation gap is the increase in education in KP. Increased secondary and tertiary education has increased the desires of the young generation to work, migrate and to equality among the sexes which sometimes goes against what the parents predetermined according to the traditional gender roles and the economic environments of the locals (Ali et al., 2024; Daraz, Bojnec, et al., 2025; Daraz, Khan, et al., 2025). Education exposes the youths to alternative perspectives of the world and this influences their perception about marriage, career and involvement in social matters.

Similarly, families and their expectations have been changed due to the urbanization and international migration as the new social experiences shape the values and lifestyles of the younger generation due to the influence of remittances (Benson, 2016; Mas' udah, 2020). Another typical feature of the households where migrants stay is that the change in the culture may hasten, which further enlarges the generation gap. The issue of generation gap is also gendered as revealed in the research studies. The rising status of girls as source of education and workforce is a battle and a bargaining ground among majority of the Pashtun societies. Parents have issues with family honor and social status that only contribute to the generation gap particularly when it comes to co-education and female mobility (Hussain, Hakim, et al., 2025; Warraich et al., 2023). Furthermore, the socialization of the young people into politics, peer groups, and online media causes the ideological divide between the youth and the older generations in the governance, religion, and the engagement in civic activities (Hussain, Hussain, et al., 2025; Loader & Loader, 2007; Mulk et al., 2025). The researches in KP reveal that generation gap has a negative and a positive outcome. On the negative side it can result in family confrontation, lack of teamwork and mental stress amongst the adolescents who feel that they are not understood. Low academic performance and withdrawal have been blamed on intergenerational tension that has not been solved. However, it is also recognized that the positive outcomes of the generation-generation negotiations are also possible since it can contribute to changing gradually the society, such as female education can become more

acceptable, or the younger generation can alter their approach to the life of the nation (Tariq & Zaman, 2025; Ullah et al., 2025). As a result, the generation gap is a source of tension as well as transition of the Pashtun society. Ideally, the KPK study is based on both modernization and social-change theories and the psychosocial models, such as the theory of identity formation by Erikson, as to why there is a break-even between cohorts (Sattar et al., 2023). Subsequent practices work with the theory of hybridity through the lens of Pashtun youths bargaining amongst the global forces and a local cultural enactment. The provided literature demonstrates that the shift in technology, education, and economy led to the development of the new repertoires of youth behavior which in most of the cases did not correspond to the expectations of the senior generations. Despite the fact that the said changes are largely regarded as sources of conflict, it is possible to consider them as the emergence of new social norms that redraw the boundaries of Pashtun identity between generations (Waqas et al., 2024). With these dynamics in mind, this paper will explore and discuss how the Pashtun society in the region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa - the influence of the rapid social change, education, and technology in bridging the intergenerational relationships and the way the interactions are mediated using the traditional cultural constructs.

Methodology

This research study utilized the positivistic approach of sociology, where the quantitative research method was adopted to conduct the study. The Malakand division was considered the site of study in which the data was gathered in the old generations and only the male individuals were selected as the part of sample that were above fifty years old and considered as the old generations. The probability sampling technique was applied in the collection of the data. In order to come up with a representative sampling of the universe, the universe was first partitioned into three districts of Lower Dir, Upper Dir and Swat and a sample was then selected using proportionate random sampling. The study sample consisted of 200 male respondents of which 60 respondents were chosen in the district of Lower Dir, 65 respondents in the district of Upper Dir and 75 respondents in the district of Swat. Data collection was done using the interview schedule. The analysis was also done using simple descriptive statistics; frequencies and percentages.

Results and Discussions

Rapid Social Change

The social transformation in the Pashtun society has become very rapid, and this has played a significant role in increasing the generation gap

between the older and the younger generations. Social change can be defined as a change in norms, values, behaviors, and lifestyles in a society over a period of time in Pashtun communities, modernization, development of technology, education, exposure to media, and globalization are some factors that cause the changes. Studies indicate that the difference in perception, values, way of life, and types of communication used between the Pashtun elders and the youth is widening as a result of such dramatic changes and hence, interpretation, conflict, and estrangement between the generations. As an example of a sociological study, supporting the results of a sociological study of the Pashtun society in Balochistan, it was discovered that the generation gap was positively correlated with social change and technological development, where older people were unable to keep up with the changing lifestyle, and younger people were more accepting towards new things and ways of life, which further divided the generation gaps (Rahim & Tareen, 2022). Likewise, technological change, shifts in lifestyle, and alterations in social norms were found to be the main factors that affect the parent-child relations among the Pashtun community in the Khyber District of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and lead to the generational conflict (Shinwari, 2025).

Table 1: Perceptions of Generational Differences and Social Change in Pashtun Society

S.NO	Statement	Yes	NO
1	Do elders believe that rapid social change is weakening traditional Pashtun values?	156(78)	44(22)
2	Do young people perceive traditional norms as restrictive in the modern era?	160(80)	40(20)
3	Is there a communication gap between parents and children due to changing lifestyles?	155(77)	45(33)
4	Do rapid economic changes influence career choices and expectations across generations?	145(72.5)	55(27.5)
5	Has respect for elders declined due to modernization and social change	135(67.5)	75(32.5)
6	Has modern education altered the attitudes and worldview of Pashtun youth compared to older generations?	160(80)	40(20)
7	Does technology and social media play a role in widening the generation gap in Pashtun society?	140(70)	60(40)
8	Has urbanization and migration affected intergenerational relations among Pashtuns?	150(75)	50(25)

9	Do changing gender roles contribute to generational conflict in Pashtun families?	160(80)	40(20)
10	Do younger and older generations differ in their perceptions of Pashtunwali under rapid social change?	155(77.5)	45(22.5)
11	Do elders believe that rapid social change is weakening traditional Pashtun values?	188(94)	22(6)
12	Is there a communication gap between parents and children due to changing lifestyles?	180(90)	20(10)
13	Has respect for elders declined due to modernization and social change?	135((67.5)	75(32.5)

Numerous works of Pashtun society reveal that the old generations tend to feel threatened by the rapid social change, particularly modernization, development of technologies, and change of the lifestyle. Based on sociological findings on Pashtun societies, the elderly often perceive that the youth use new concepts, new practices, and exposure to foreign culture as taking them out of the rich cultural traditions over time like respect to elders, shared responsibility and social institutions that are indigenous. The case study of social change and generation gap in Pashtun society states that when older people were questioned about the gap between generations they state that the gap is growing and that the youth have less willingness to accept the traditional family norms and way of living posing the risk of values and behavioral change. This is a more generalized assumption of elders that fast social transformation is beginning to tear the cultural fabric that once united the community together (Yazdani & Ghaderi, 2011). It is also observed by researchers that employers such as the hujra, the traditional social space where values, norms, and customs are passed down across generations, are facing the pressure of urbanization and shifting lifestyles, which is one of the reasons elders develop an understanding of cultural decay (Niazi et al., 2021). Assimilarly, most of the surveyed over 50+ 156 (78) considered that the generation gap has traditional values of Pashtun culture on the weekends, Nang (Honor), Badal (Justice/Revenge), Melmastia (Hospitality, Nanawatai (Asylum), Respect for Elders, Collectivism and Kinship: Family, clan (khel), and tribe (qawm) are the main units in the society, Jirga System, Bravery and Courage (Tura) Pamir, E As a whole, the cultural values of the Traditional Pashtun encourage social integrity, moral accountability, and group survival (Bangash & Habib, 2022). Nevertheless, modernization, education, urbanization, and globalization are becoming certain values that challenge

these values, resulting in cultural change and even tension between generations (Ali, 2021).

According to empirical and sociological research conducted on the Pashtun society, it is evident that the older generations feel threatened by the speed at which social change is taking place as a danger to the traditional cultural values and social institutions. Social norms have changed especially among the younger Pashtuns due to the force of modernization, technological development, shifting lifestyles, and exposure to the global culture which made the elders feel that the long-established traditions were slowly becoming extinct (Kabiri, 2012). The behavior of the youth, including challenging authority, focusing on personal interests, and living a modern lifestyle, is perceived as a way of alienating the elderly members to the traditional values of the Pashtun like respecting seniors, fulfilling communal duties, and collective identity.

According to Shinwari (2025), older respondents explicitly recognized the growing generation gap as they noticed that young people were less cooperative with traditional family norms and cultural values. This view indicates that elders are concerned about the fact that social change is happening at a tremendously high pace and have been undermining the moral and cultural structure, which in the past ensured social cohesion within Pashtun village. This impression is aggravated by the weakening of the traditional institutions especially the hujra. The hujra was traditionally a community socialization place that allowed intergenerational interaction and cultural values transmission. Nevertheless, urbanization and evolving lifestyles have diminished its applicability, which confirms the elderly people with their cultural degradation (Rahim & Tareen, 2022).

These perceptions are also supported by quantitative evidence. According to Pamir et al. (2023), most of the respondents aged 50 and above (78% n=156) said that the generation gap has undermined the core Pashtun cultural values including Nang (honor), Badal (justice/revenge), Melmastia (hospitality), Nanawatai (asylum), respect towards the aged, collectivism and kinship (khel and qawm), the jirga system, and Tura (bravery and courage). This observation reveals that not only do the elders notice the cultural change, but they also correlate it with the difference in generations in regard to values and behavior.

Conventionally, these cultural values were important towards ensuring social cohesion, moral responsibility, and collective survival within the Pashtun society (Hussain, 2025). But modern pressures like education, urbanization, globalization, and media coverage have changed the social orientations, mostly towards the young generation, leading to

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tension between generations and cultures instead of direct continuity (S. Ali et al., 2025). Therefore, the generational gap is not just a clash between generations but a larger culture change in the Pashtun society.

The sudden social changes in the Pasadena society especially modernization, urbanization, and exposure to the media of the world have led to a communication gap between the children and the parents. Historically, families were structured in a hierarchical way with the seniors determining norms and values which were never challenged. Nevertheless, as the younger generations are educated and exposed to modern lifestyle, their respect of traditional authority increases, causing misunderstandings and decreased intergenerational communication (Rahim & Tareen, 2022). Research indicates that urbanized Pashtun families have more common conflict situations about everyday life, career, and education options, which is an indication of a decline in channels of parent-child communication (Pamir et al., 2023). On the same note, majority 140 (70) of the respondents held the view that the Rapid social changes experienced in the Pashtun society especially the modernization, urbanization and exposure to world media have led to the development of a communication gap between the parents and children. Traditional Pasifika culture is hierarchical and in this community, the elders especially the parents have power in making decisions regarding children in areas of education, marriage, career, and social behavior. Respect to the elder, obedience and the family values instilled in the cultural structure of Pashtunwali, and this attribute in the past guaranteed a hassle free communication and intergenerational comprehension (Ahmed, 2012; Barth, 1965).

Things have however changed with the shift of lifestyles, brought about by modernization, urbanization, formal education, and global media exposure, which have changed the pattern of communication between parents and children. The younger generations of the Pashtuns, particularly the educated and urbanized generations are getting influenced by individualistic and globalized concepts. They will challenge traditional values, bargain individual decisions, and embrace contemporary societal trends, potentially causing conflicts or disagreement with the aged (Rahim & Tareen, 2022).

Research shows that the changes are seen by the older generations as a disruption of the traditional communication channels. As an example, older people say that young people are not eager to seek their advice or even listen to the parental decision about the career choice, choice in marriage or even the family issues. It is not only a behavioral difference,

but a dissimilarity in principles and world-view across the generations (Pamir et al., 2023).

The communication gap is increased further by the urbanization factor. In the same vein, majority 180 (90) of the respondents contended that there is a communication rift between parents and children as a result of shifting lifestyles. The extended family and communal living of rural Pashtun communities helped in the unceasing interaction and mentorship of the elders. The trends of urbanization and migration have promoted the nuclear family structure, diminishing the amount of generation-to-generation communication and undermining the power of parental wisdom (Ali, 2021; Masood, 2024).

To conclude, communication gap in Pashtun families is a direct impact of the changing lifestyles at a very fast rate. It draws attention to the conflict between the hierarchical and traditional social frameworks and modern and individualistic principles embraced by young people. Such gap is not only the behavioral phenomenon but the more profound cultural negotiation between tradition and modernity. The swift movement of economies through migration, urbanization and economic employment, and entry to new occupations have greatly altered the expectations and choices of occupations across the generations. In this connection, the respondents 145(72.5), also perceived that rapid economic changes determine the career choices and expectations at different generations. Unlike the use of vocational or family-related jobs that supported the economy of the collective clan (khel) or tribal (qawm) by elders, younger Pashtuns focus on education, professional and economic freedom (Amin, 2023). These disparities in economic orientation further add to generational conflicts and are also the cause of the feeling of value differences between the older and younger generations.

The respect of the elders has been put into question by modernization, education and exposure to global norms and this is also true of the 135 ((67.5) respondents that the respect to the elders also decreased, because of modernization and social change which was a fundamental unit of the social structure of the Pashtun. The younger Pashtuns are increasingly demanding independence in their personal, education and employment choices and challenging the authority of the elders. Elders see this as a drop in morals and social solidarity, which increases the generation gap even more (Hussain, 2025).

The current education has changed the attitudes of the Pashtun youth and altered their worldviews to be more individualistic, critical, and global in outlook. Moreover, most of the respondents (160(80) suggested that the

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attitudes and worldview of the Pashtun youth were changed due to the modern education in comparison with the older generations. Elders believe in traditional values, Nang (honor) and collective identity unlike educated young who believe in personal achievement and social mobility, which brings ideological disparity and generational conflict (Khan, 2022).

The use of technology and social media is one of the critical issues that increase the generation gap. On the same note, majority 140(70) of the respondents mentioned that technology and social media contribute to the generation gap within the Pashtun society. The young people are being exposed to the world culture, alternative lifestyles, and new social norms which in many ways are at variance with the traditional Pashtun values. The elders commonly see such exposure as a loss of respect toward elders, collective responsibility, and cultural sustainability (Pamir et al., 2023). Traditional extended-family system has been undone by urbanization and migration and it is now interacting less with the generation. The nuclear families are more prevalent in cities, and the young people are introduced to the world of individualism, and this leads to the weakening of the authority of elders and the decline of communal values like jirga attendance or hujra meeting (Ahmed, 2012; Cheema, 2022).

Intergenerational conflict is further aggravated by the change of gender roles due to education and involvement in the labor market, where women do not serve in the family homemaker role, or their movement is limited, as a threat to the family honor (Nang) and cultural integrity (Barth, 1965; Hussain, 2025).

Under the changing social conditions, younger and older generations are becoming more different in the understanding of the Pashtunwali. Young people tend to selectively follow the code with the focus on equality, education, and professional ethics, whereas older people still focus on obedience, collective identity, and traditional conflict-resolving mechanisms (Rahim & Tareen, 2022). In general, the elders feel that a high rate of social change is undermining the traditional Pashtun values such as honor, justice, hospitality, asylum, and respect of the elderly, kinship, the jirga system, and bravery (Tura). Such a view is supported by a decreased level of conformity to conventional norms of the young generations and the weakening of such cultural institutions as the hujra (Pamir et al., 2023).

All in all, the cultural shift in the Pashtun society is largely motivated by the generation gap. Older people feel that the current social change, in terms of modernization, education, urbanization, and exposure to the media weakens traditional values, social cohesion, and moral responsibility. Meanwhile, young people embrace an individualistic and globalized culture

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and orientation, which leads to an ongoing negation and bargaining between tradition and modernity and not cultural continuity. Among the main signs, there are a lack of respect towards older people, the shift in gender roles, the modification of career expectations, communication barriers, and redefinition of Pashtunwali.

Conclusion

The Pashtun society analysis proves that the generation gap is one of the key factors that promote cultural change. The result of the shift in social structure via modernization, education, urbanization, and exposure to mass media is that older generations view traditional values like *Nang* (honor), *Badal* (justice/revenge), *Melmastia* (hospitality), *Nanawatai* (asylum), respect towards the aged, collectivism, kinship, the jirga system, and *Tura* (bravery and courage) as a threat to traditional Pashtun values. The young generations, with their ideological and behavioral differences with the older generation, tend to follow individualistic and globally orient This dislocation takes a number of forms, including less communication and consultation between generations within families, more difficulty in career and economic priorities, more modification in gender roles and family duties, and selective conformity to Pashtunwali and traditional regulations. All in all, the generation gap is not only a clash of age-groups but it is also a greater negotiation process between tradition and modernity, where tradition keeps on and modernity adapts to modern day social realities.

Recommendations

Rebirth of Traditional Institutions

Enhance the influence of community areas like the *hujra* to facilitate intergenerational communication and passing of cultural expectations in a manner that can be adapted to the contemporary life.

Advertising Family Communication Programs.

Introduction of community-based programs, aimed at the participatory dialog between parents and children, with attention to mutual respect, understanding, and bargaining over modern and traditional values.

Cultural Values together with Modern Curriculum Education.

Incorporate the values of Pashtunwali and the traditions of the local culture into the school programs whereby the young people learn the importance of the traditional culture in addition to adopting the new knowledge.

Community Activities between Generations.

Promote youth and elder projects Could youth and elder projects can be promoted by having them do things together like cultural events, local development projects or conflict-resolution exercises to reinforce social cohesion and respect towards the elders.

Using Technology and Media responsibly.

Create awareness on the cultural implications of technology and social media and make young people remain connected to the culture even as they interact with international networks.

Negotiated Gender Roles

Through these measures, the Pashtun society will be able to alleviate the impacts of the generation gap whereby modernization and exposure to the outside world do not destroy traditional values but rather they exist with them to promote social cohesion, moral accountability, and continuity of culture.

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